

THE ISSUE OF EDUCATED YOUTH IN THE ACTIVITIES OF JADIDISTS

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Annotation. The article expresses an opinion about the socio-political situation at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, and the emergence of the Jadidist movement in such a difficult period. At the same time, an analysis of the ideas of young people to learn and become enlightened is presented on the example of the works of artists such as Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdurauf Fitrat, Behbudi, who lived and created in this period. Reactions to the given works were expressed and concluding remarks were made.

Keywords. History, science, enlightenment, national liberation, youth.

It is not a secret to anyone that our nation, which gave the world many scientists in every field, such as Ibn Sina, Beruni, Zamakhshari, Khorezmi, Mirza Ulugbek, turned towards backwardness and went through a sad period. In such a difficult situation, an intellectual who was not indifferent to the fate of the country, who fought for national liberation, sought enlightenment, aspired for independence, made it his destiny to improve education and upbringing, to raise a well-rounded, mature generation. The layer has matured. These were Jadidists. At the end of the 19th century, Jadidism emerged in Crimea under the leadership of Ismailbek Gasprinsky through the newspaper "Tarjimon". Jadidism, which was widespread in Turkey and Iran, later entered Turkestan as a result of the efforts of Behbudi, Fitrat, Cholpon, Qadiri, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov and many others.

If the old-timers were one scourge, the Bolsheviks, who were now settling down, were another scourge. The modernists had to protect and save their people, their children, first of all, from the inappropriate superstitions and old-fashioned views of the ancients, and secondly, from the policy of the Bolsheviks aimed at stifling all our freedom. Therefore, they first of all started the work by making the children and the people literate and opening their eyes. In this way, they worked in three directions. Education (opening schools, creating textbooks), literature (creating works for national liberation), theater

(staging works created from the life of the people and presenting them to the people). They turned knowledge, literature, and art into their main weapons to wake up the people and get them out of the swamp. In this article, we have analyzed the works published in the way of educating the youth and population.

Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov was a leader of Jadidists, a person who fought for the freedom of the people and was one of the first enemies of the Soviet government. He opens martial arts schools, he himself writes textbooks for schools such as “The First Teacher” and “The Second Teacher”. He strongly condemns the fathers among our compatriots who do not send their children to school, depriving them of knowledge and becoming servants of the Russians, and supports the fathers who take their children by the hand and take them to school. However, he regrets that sometimes teachers are not well-educated. In Abdurashidkhanov Munavvarqori’s poem “Laziness is our enemy” (M. Abdurashidkhanov, 2022, p. 111):

Get up, comrades! It’s time for us to work.

We are all young workers, our workplace is a school garden

Get up, let’s get to work quickly,

Let’s get rid of laziness!

the words are said, and it is meant that the first task is to acquire knowledge. In the course of the poem, while urging people to get rid of laziness and learn, he says, “The youth will protect the country’s reputation”. He believes that every sign of a living soul is to study, to be excited, to lose laziness. The poet considers our evil to be laziness and ignorance, and not to fight against them is cowardice. Ignorance comes from laziness, it is inevitable to face ignorance as a result of ignorance, that’s why the poet opposes these vices in this poem and calls for knowledge. The development of young people in all aspects and the acquisition of knowledge is one of the relevant topics even today. After all, our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev says about this: “The future of our planet, its well-being depends on how our children grow up to be human beings. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential” (Mirziyoyev 219). Because an educated, intelligent, spiritual child is the wealth of the country.

“O brothers, oh my countrymen!!! We should open our eyes from the sleep of ignorance and look around us. In this age, when every nation is satisfied with the death of knowledge as the first means to protect its happiness and prospects, if we continue in this negligence and ignorance, our prospects are extremely dangerous. There is no doubt that we will die laughing at the whole world”

(Abdurashidkhanov M. 2022, p. 111). Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov writes the books “Sabzazor”, “The surface of the earth”, “Tajvidal Qur’an” and his textbooks are taught in schools of the new method. Nation will never forget their children who gave their lives for their nation and their name will always live in our hearts.

At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, Abdurauf Fitrat has a great place among Cholpan, Qadiri, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, and Behbudi, who widely promoted the fields of national press, theater, education, art, and enlightenment. Fitrat traveled to Turkey, Arabia, India and studied medicine in Istanbul. After receiving education in Istanbul, Fitrat's worldview, who had a good impression of the socio-political and educational aspects of other countries, changed dramatically. He went to Turkey and published the works “Discussion”, “Sayha”, “Statement of an Indian tourist” and secretly brought them to Bukhara and distributed them to young Bukharans. His poem called “Ogut” was addressed to the youth of that time. It is not just an appeal, it is a call to the youth of today and the future generation to fight for the homeland and protect it.

A calm man, in your beautiful, bright eyes
I read about the happiness of this nation.
In your thinking, standing and yourself
I see the courage to fight for this country.

After all, despite the pressures of the tsarist Russia, which is always on the lookout and is ready to destroy as soon as possible, along with other fighters, “don't rush in, don't be afraid, don't be afraid, don't make a fuss!” It is clear that these words of Fitrat, who is openly appealing, made the colonial state afraid. Because Fitrat and others like him would stop at nothing for enlightenment and national liberation. At the beginning of the sentence, the poet who addresses the young men as “heavy guy”, why did he use the quality “heavy” in relation to them? It is known that the Uzbek people are known as very simple and kind people. It is not surprising that the word “heavy” comes in the meaning of “burden” and refers to the same thing. That is why Fitrat uses this word in an exaggeration, referring to the time of agitation, burning. In the poem “Ogut”, the poet said that he sees the happiness of the nation in their “beautiful” and “bright” eyes, he also mentions that the country will be saved, i.e. liberated, and he means that all his hopes are in the youth. As Fitrat is a person of the new age, he should destroy, burn and tear the old views that hold some people back from development, that do not benefit people at all, and some of the perfidious actions

of officials in the poem “Old clouds blocking the way of nation”. says to drop it, burn, and tear down. That is, he likens these views to an old cloud. At the end, Misra (a line of words on the poem) wrote the words that came out of his heart, saying that if he could not do these things, it would be a shame for them, “Fall, disappear, go!” he ends his speech. These sentences are similar to Usman Nasir's poem “Heart” (Usman Nasir 1959, p. 134). After all, Usman Nasir also wrote in his heart that if the country does not like you, “Lightning up, turn into lightning, lightening up!” “Let me just die,” he orders. Similarly, the unpatriotic young man, his heart, who needs it and why. Isn't it humiliating for him? Such beautiful poems of Fitrat will never disappear from the history of our literature.

Mahnudhoja Behbudi, who spent his life to raise the culture, development, and enlightenment of our people, was one of the first jadidchilas and his life was spent in many difficulties. Behbudi, who fought for freedom with the slogan “Rights are earned, not given” (Karimov N. 2008, p. 37), organizes free libraries, schools, theaters for the education of our people. He opens various charitable societies and sends young people to study with the money received from them. “Rich people of other nations build schools and orphanages for the poor and orphans, and appoint endowment scholarships for the education of the poor and orphans... Ours are proud of their marriages, marriages, and weddings. There are even rich people who do not educate their sons. The end of this departure is bad, it is necessary to study and teach” (Behbudi 1913, pp. 4-5), the people laments thinking about their children. Behbudi first staged his own drama “Padarkush” (Behbudi 2009, pp. 40-51) in the theater he opened. This drama of Behbudi is also called “The case of an uneducated child”. Let's dwell on the title of the work. Padarkush means "father killer". The very word “man” makes a person shudder when he hears it. The second name shows that this is the result of lack of knowledge and enlightenment. In the work, the idea of enlightenment is promoted through a teacher and an intellectual. At the beginning of the play, the teacher comes to the house of the intellectual rich man and tells him to teach his child. A rich person says that “the foundation of the world is based on wealth and the rich are respected” We can witness that people prefer the rich to the mullah (an educated Muslim trained in religious law and doctrine and usually holding an official post). In these sentences, it is shown how much the nation is becoming inferior, people behave according to money. If he had studied, he would not have helped to kill his father, and he would not have been exiled to Sibr and received the label of padarkush (person who killed his own father). As a result of lack of education, a family was in disarray. This is not a

tragedy of a single family, but a tragedy of an entire nation. After all, Tashmurad's friends and accomplices were young people. Not only Tashmurad did not study, his parents did not study either, when they did, they taught their children and brought them up well. After all, a child takes an example from his parents. Naturally, everything goes back to education. When the nation is knowledgeable, its future will be bright and happy. The work promotes enlightenment from beginning to end. At the end of the work, the intellectual said, "This is the fate of children without knowledge and education. If his father had taught him these things, this crime and infidelity would not have happened and he would not have become a drunkard. As long as we are not disciplined and do not educate our children, bad events and misfortunes will happen," he addresses everyone, so it is not surprising that Behbudi spoke his words to the people through intellectuals.

In short, the manifestations of modern literature are the main reasons for our prosperous, bright life, free and free living today. Jadidists used all their capabilities and created immortal works, not only artistic charm, but also ideas such as freedom, enlightenment, patriotism, and the knowledge of young people shone at the heart of them. Every word they say rings in our ears like fertilizer. It is the duty of young people like us to be a generation worthy of our enlightened ancestors.

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